

A Comparative Time Series Analysis of the ARIMA and Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) Models

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Abstract

Several new transformer-based time series models have been developed in the past 5 years and research has provided evidence of these models' superior performance compared to classic statistical models such as ARIMA. While transformer-based models show impressive performance on baseline datasets, there has been no research done on the robustness of these models on datasets with controlled modifications and in a replicable manner. In this paper, the Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) model was compared to the classical statistical model ARIMA on simulated data using multiple horizons. Data were simulated using a linear combination of exogenous variables; in total, 50 realizations of 52,704 observations were simulated. The comparison tests, which included controlled modifications, include 1) a baseline comparison on the simulated data, 2) simulated data with reduced noise, 3) simulated data with increased noise, 4) a reduction of training data, and 5) a nonlinear combination of the target variable. The TFT and ARIMA models were compared using mean squared error (MSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) on various horizons. Results show that the ARIMA produces lower average error metrics than the TFT across all horizons and under all modified conditions.

Key Words: time series, ARIMA, temporal fusion transformer, TFT

1. Introduction

In contrast with independently sampled data, time series data consist of observations recorded sequentially overtime with each observation potentially being dependent on preceding values. In time series analysis, it is often possible to observe multiple datasets representing the same underlying phenomenon under different conditions or time periods; each of these datasets is referred to as a realization. While time series data allow for analysis and explanation of historical patterns, many applications seek to also predict future values based on past observations. Forecasting refers to predicting values beyond the final observed time point and has applications across diverse domains, including finance (Mozaffari & Zhang, 2024), meteorology (Haque et al., 2021), retail, healthcare, and economics (Lim et al., 2021). An example of time series data is daily stock market data for a specific stock, whereby one may want to forecast stock prices for the next week.

There are two main classes of time series data: univariate and multivariate. Univariate datasets only contain one dependent variable that varies with time. In the stock market example, a univariate series might consist solely of the closing price of a stock recorded at regular intervals. In contrast, multivariate datasets not only contain a variable of interest (also known as the dependent variable or the target variable), but contain other variables called exogenous variables which may also vary based on time. In the stock market example, a multivariate series might consist of the closing price, maximum price per day, minimum price per day, and volume. Exogenous variables can be strongly correlated to the dependent variable, weakly correlated, or have no correlation at all. Multivariate

time series are thus more similar to traditional linear regression problems, but with the data varying at a fixed period of time.

An important feature of time series analysis, and forecasting specifically, is the forecasting horizon. This is the amount of time steps into the future that the model must predict. An example that illustrates this concept is weather predictions. A short-term forecast with a horizon of a few hours or a day is expected to be more accurate than a long-term forecast with a horizon of 7 or even 10 days. Generally, these longer forecasts may be less accurate than short-term forecasts.

Since the mid-1900's statistical approaches have been used to understand and forecast both univariate and multivariate time series datasets. These approaches include models such as exponential smoothing, Holt Winters, and autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) (Makridakis et al., 2020). These approaches are statistical in nature because they use the underlying structure of the data for modeling and forecasting.

The ARIMA(p,d,q) model in particular is commonly used today as a baseline statistical model when doing comparisons. It is composed of three components: autoregressive (AR), integrated (I), and moving average (MA).

$$AR(p) * I(d) * y_t = MA(q) * \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

The AR(p) term measures the model's relationship to past data. For example, if the model is only influenced by data points 1 period in the past, then $p = 1$. The I(d) term can be used to determine the period. For example, monthly data that repeats annually will have a value of $d = 12$. y is the value of the time series at time t . The MA(q) term is used to measure the model's relationship to past error terms (ε). For example, if the model is only influenced by errors from 1 time period ago, then $q = 1$. It is a relatively simple and easy to understand model that allows for trends in the data, seasonality, as well as a structured way for past data to affect future data.

While these statistical models have been foundational in time series forecasting, advances in computational power and data availability have opened the door for alternative modeling strategies. Starting around the turn of the century, machine learning approaches saw increasing adoption. Some examples include Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) which includes the long short-term memory (LSTM) approach (Ahmed et al., 2023). Even approaches that use decision trees such as Random Forest or XGBoost have been used for time series forecasting (Schmid et al., 2024). These approaches differ from statistical models in that they make fewer assumptions about the data's underlying structure, thereby making them particularly useful when that structure is not well understood. Compared to statistical models, machine learning approaches often need considerably more training data to perform well and are computationally more intensive.

In the past decade, deep neural networks (DNN) have grown rapidly in popularity. These types of models use several layers of neural networks, which allows them to be particularly adept at modeling highly nonlinear data. However, DNNs require substantially more training data and significantly greater computation resources compared to previously mentioned machine learning approaches. Some recent models that fall into this category are DeepAR (Salinas et al., 2020), TiDE (Das et al., 2023), TSMixer (Chen et al., 2023), and DPMN (Olivares et al., 2024). These models have shown impressive preliminary results, but due to relatively recent development, there is minimal comprehensive evaluation of the models.

Additional examples of DNNs include Transformers and self-attention mechanisms. Though originally designed for natural language processing, these DNN architectures have been adapted for use in time series forecasting tasks. Examples of adapted architectures include Autoformer, Informer, and Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) (Ahmed et al., 2023). In particular, TFT has shown itself to be a promising time series algorithm. In the past few years, it has been used with

success in applications as varied as anomaly detection (Ayhan et al., 2024), air temperature in railway carriages (Feng et al., 2022), battery capacity (Gomez et al., 2024), and streamflow (Rasiya & Roy, 2024).

Although the machine learning and DNN approaches were developed more recently than statistical approaches, they do not always yield better results. These models often take considerably more computation time, require substantially larger training data, and are prone to overfitting. Statistical approaches remain widely used and are frequently incorporated into ensemble methods that combine multiple models.

Over the years, various methods have been used to compare both statistical and machine learning models. A straightforward approach is to compare the forecasting accuracy of models on different datasets. This approach has grown into large-scale forecasting competitions, where participants submit models to be tested on dozens, or even hundreds, of time series datasets. One of the most well-known examples is the M Competitions, organized by Spyros Makridakis (Hyndman, 2020).

In addition to forecasting competitions, researchers sometimes use simulated data to evaluate the models. Data simulation offers a controlled and efficient alternative to collecting large numbers of real-world datasets. It allows for the easy generation of many realizations, enabling systematic comparisons across multiple error metrics. Simulations also make it possible to manipulate specific data properties, such as the amount of error or noise. These types of controlled modifications are often very difficult or impossible with real-world datasets. By generating a dataset with simulated data, the error and noise characteristics are known and can provide a basis for structured and reproducible analysis.

Another model evaluation method is varying the length of the training data. This method is generally straightforward as it involves increasing or decreasing the size of the training data to assess how it impacts forecasting performance. Specific to time series tasks, this can be done by reducing the number of periods included in the training window. Adjusting the training horizon can help reveal differences in model performance for short-term versus long-term forecasts.

The amount of training data required varies by modeling approach. In general, statistical models require less data than machine learning models, which in turn require less than DNNs. However, the exact amount of training data needed will depend on the model and the application. For instance, transformer-based models often require extremely large datasets but can leverage graphical processing units (GPUs) to train more efficiently (Ahmed et al., 2023).

Model performance is typically evaluated using error metrics that quantify the difference between predicted and actual values. Common examples in time series forecasting are mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). Mean absolute error (MAE) is defined as

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |y_t - \hat{y}_t| \quad (2)$$

where y is the true value of the datapoint and \hat{y} is the predicted value. The formula for MAE metric is straightforward and easy to interpret. Mean squared error (MSE) is similar but squares the errors and thus places more weight on the large errors.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2 \quad (3)$$

For a scale independent error metrics, researchers will often use mean absolute percentage error (MAPE).

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{y_t - \hat{y}_t}{y_t} \right| \quad (4)$$

Since transformer-based architectures have only emerged in the last decade, comprehensive evaluations of their performance, particularly in time series forecasting, remain limited. Existing studies typically compare them with other models on a small set of datasets, without testing their robustness under systematically varied conditions in a scalable and replicable manner (Oliveira & Ramos, 2024; Zhou et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022). Controlling the modifications, such as differing levels of error variance and amount of training data, will allow for a more nuanced look at how a transformer-based model compares with a more statistical approach to time series modeling. In this research, data is simulated to study the effects of increased and decreased noise, a reduction in training set size, and data with nonlinear behavior. MSE and MAE are used to compare the effects of these controlled modifications on the transformer-based TFT model and the ARIMA model.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Transformer-Based Models for Time Series

In the past two decades, several machine learning approaches have been introduced to time series modeling and forecasting (Song et al., 2017). Notably, and central to this research, the use of transformer-based models and self-attention mechanisms have also been adapted for use in time series forecasting tasks (Ahmed et al., 2023). While the Transformer architecture was originally introduced for natural language processing (NLP), the Transformer has been successfully adapted to time series forecasting due to its ability to use data sequentially (Ahmed et al., 2023). Unlike traditional and older NLP models, the Transformer allows language to be processed unrestricted to positional order (Ahmed et al., 2023). Additionally, due to the Transformer's ability to be parallelizable and thus extremely efficient with the use of GPUs, large time series datasets can be handled more efficiently (Vaswani et al., 2017). Existing research on applications of Transformers to time series cases include the transformer-based architectures: Temporal Fusion Transformer (Lim et al., 2021), Informer (Zhou et al., 2021), LogSparse Transformer (Ahmed et al., 2023), Autoformer (Wu et al., 2021), and Simply Attend and Diagnose ("SAnD"; Song et al., 2017).

Some research has been conducted to evaluate various transformer-based architectures. Oliveira and Ramos (2024) examine the performance of Transformers, Informers, Autoformers, temporal fusion Transformers (TFT), and PatchTST by applying the models to real-world retail data provided by the M5 competition. Researchers compare the time series forecasting results of Transformer models to baseline models (AutoARIMA, AutoETS, seasonal naïve, and naïve) and find that the transformer-based models had superior performance in forecasting compared to the baseline models. They used the MASE (mean absolute scaled error) and WQL (weighted quantile loss) metrics and determined that the transformer-based models had a MASE improvement of 26% to 29% and reductions in WQL up to 34% (Oliveira & Ramos, 2024).

While the application of Transformers to time series forecasting tasks have certainly contributed to the field, some researchers are skeptical of its performance. Zeng et al. (2023) question the validity of the research around transformer-based solutions for long-term time series forecasting (LTSF). Due to the permutation-invariant and "anti-order" self-attention mechanisms used in Transformers, researchers assert that the use of Transformers on LTSF tasks are bound to cause temporal information loss (Zeng et al., 2023). This is cause for concern with LTSF tasks since the order of the continuous set of points in time series data is central to forecasting (Zeng et al., 2023).

Zeng et al. (2023) also point out that existing research around the performance of transformer-based LSTF has been only evaluated against performance autoregressive or iterated multi-step models which can have significant error accumulation with time series data. As such, researchers evaluated transformer-based LTSF solutions against direct multi-step (DMS) forecasting and ultimately found that the DMS forecasting had lower mean squared error (MSE) than transformer-based solutions.

This was consistent for horizons of 96-, 192-, 336-, and 720-time steps and across the nine datasets that were evaluated including weather, electricity, and traffic datasets (Zeng et al., 2023).

2.2 Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT)

As a solution to the complexity of various inputs involved in multi-horizon time series forecasting, the Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) was developed (Lim et al., 2021). The TFT aims to provide a solution to handling various inputs, such as static covariates, future inputs, and exogenous variables, by using specialized components (Lim et al., 2021). These components are: 1) sequence-to-sequence and attention-based temporal processing components, 2) static covariate encoders, 3) gating components, 4) variable selection, and 5) quantile predictions (Lim et al., 2021). In addition, the attention mechanism allows TFT to show which variables have higher importance, which can be helpful for model interpretability (Lim et al., 2021).

Lim et al. (2021) applied the TFT to real-world datasets in the sectors of electricity, traffic, retail, and volatility, and used a simple univariate time series data set as a baseline. The researchers find that the TFT outperforms the baseline performance in forecasting accuracy. Several other researchers have also found that the use of TFT improved the forecasting performance for problems ranging from anomaly detection (Ayhan et al., 2024), air temperature in railway carriages (Feng et al., 2022), battery capacity (Gomez et al., 2024), and streamflow (Rasiya & Roy, 2024). The ability to forecast highly non-linear data as well as its relative performance on extremely large datasets is mentioned as a benefit for this model (Lim et al., 2021).

Other research has been conducted to examine whether the TFT architecture is capable of capturing short- and long-term temporal dependencies (Zhang et al., 2022). This was done by applying the TFT to forecast freeway speed with short-term (5 minute) and long-term (150 minute) horizons, and comparing forecasting performance against ARIMA, MLP, support vector machines, and Recurrent Neural Network as benchmark models (Zhang et al., 2022). When compared to other models' predictions, the TFT appeared to perform best when forecasting horizons are greater than 30 minutes (Zhang et al., 2022). In this examination of TFT, researchers find the specific advantages of the TFT to be: 1) ability to consider static input, known input, and observation inputs, 2) use of self-attention mechanism to capture short- and long-term time correlation, and 3) better prediction performance when horizon is greater than 60 minutes (Zhang et al., 2022). The interpretability of the model due to inclusion of variable importance was also cited as a benefit of TFT (Rasiya & Roy, 2024). Zhang et al. (2022) notes that one disadvantage of the TFT is the large amount of training data needed.

Some researchers have attempted to enhance traditional TFT architecture. Gomez et al. (2024) introduced an improved Temporal Fusion Transformer (ITFT) architecture to increase prediction accuracy. The ITFT is based on bidirectional memory long short-term memory (Bi-LSTM) encoder-decoder layer, which uses a Bayesian optimization hyperparameter for model tuning (Gomez et al., 2024). Researchers find that the ITFT achieves higher prediction accuracy due to the model's ability to better capture random deviations (Gomez et al., 2024).

Feng et al. (2022) developed an improved TFT by using two new components: 1) double-convolutional residual encoder, and 2) spatio-temporal double-gated structure. Compared to the original TFT model, the improved TFT developed by Feng et al. (2022) improved the mean absolute percentage error by 21.7% and 11.7% on two separate high-speed rail air conditioning time series datasets.

2.3 Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)

The ARIMA model is commonly used as a standard for model comparison in the time series field and has been used extensively in time series forecasting research (Makridakis et al., 2020; Oliveira & Ramos, 2024; Zhang et al., 2022). Though, indeed one of the oldest and most widely used time series models, there are clear limitations to the ARIMA. These limitations are namely: 1) the assumption that future values are linearly related to the past and with white noise, and 2) the need for large amounts of historical data to predict accurately (Khashei et al., 2008). Additionally, more recent research is beginning to shed light on newer models that may achieve better forecasting

accuracy. For example, researchers are finding that combining various methods greatly improves prediction accuracy when compared to the stand-alone ARIMA model (Makridakis et al., 2020; Khashei et al., 2008).

2.4 Data Simulations

The use of simulated data is especially useful in methodological research, particularly because it allows for the comparison of the time series models independent of uncertainties in the data (Dakos et al., 2012). As such, the simulated data will be used for illustrative purposes (i.e., proof of concept) in this research. Unlike with real-world data, simulated data sets allow researchers to evaluate models on data with deliberate modifications and compare the models accordingly. Some existing methodological research in data science that utilizes simulated data include: the comparison of traditional statistical vs. machine learning approaches (Bonilla et al., 2023; Schmid et al., 2024), and the comparison of random forest vs. logistic regression (Kirasich et al., 2018). Though there is not as much time series research available that uses simulated data, there is extensive research on the evaluation of time series models using real-world data.

Makridakis Competitions (also known as M Competitions) are time series forecasting competitions in which several real-world datasets are selected and used to evaluate various time series models. The M Competitions are designed to provide a fair evaluation of forecasting techniques and to gauge the state of the state of such techniques (Makridakis et al., 2020). Researchers at M Competitions regularly choose their own real-world datasets to show the effectiveness of their algorithm and restrict it to very few datasets.

At the M4 Competition (2018), 100,000 different time series data sets were used to evaluate primarily statistical methods and a few machine learning models. The best participants used a combination of statistical and machine learning forecasts in an ensemble approach; pure machine learning models performed poorly (Makridakis et al., 2020). The following M5 Competition (2020) used real-world retail datasets, instead of the large number of varied datasets used in the M4 competition. In this competition, the machine learning approach LightGBM was used by most of the top performing participants. This algorithm uses gradient boosted trees and exogenous variables. In general, use of exogenous variables was noted as improving model performance greatly (Makridakis et al., 2022).

The most recent M6 Competition (2022) used real-world financial time series datasets. Similar to the previous M5 Competition, more machine learning approaches were featured among the top performers. Machine learning models mentioned included: a Bayesian dynamic factor model with heteroskedasticity, XGBoost, and AutoTS. Even though machine learning approaches were successful, the top 20% of performers featured a roughly equal number of statistical time series approaches (Makridakis et al., 2024).

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3. Methods

In order to truly evaluate the model and introduce noise and other components in a systematic way, data were simulated in this study. Though simulated indeed, the data was generated so that it

resembles the real-world and widely used weather dataset¹ (Wu et al., 2021). This allows for the models to be developed and evaluated with practical considerations in mind. Additionally, simulated data with real-world applications and patterns can help make the results more easily comparable to existing research.

Simulating data allows for the generation of several realistic simulations of the dependent variable and exogenous variables, while knowing the true value of the dependent variable. Real data sets have implicit noise in the dependent variables which cannot be known; generating the noise through data simulation allows for the noise variance to be altered. This allows one to pinpoint the effects of the noise or the increased variance in the models. For this study, air temperature (degrees Celsius) was predicted using maximum vapor pressure and dew point temperature.

3.1 Weather Data Set

Simulated data were guided by the real-world weather dataset (Wu et al., 2021) that has 52,704 total observations with a date column, 21 numeric feature columns, and air temperature (degrees Celsius) as the target variable. Plotting the data, as shown in Figure 1., reveals both an annual periodic trend and a daily periodic trend, consistent with known seasonal and daily temperature patterns. Figure 2 provides a closer look at a single week of data, highlighting the daily trends and fluctuations.

Figure 1: Air temperature (°C) recorded over the full year beginning January 1, 2020. The data exhibit a pronounced seasonal pattern, with temperatures rising steadily through the spring, peaking during the summer months (around day 200), and declining in the fall. Daily temperature fluctuations are visible throughout the year.

¹ The referenced weather dataset may be found at: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Tc7GeVN7DLEl-RAs-JVwG9yFMf--S8dy/view?usp=drive_link

Figure 2: Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) measured over the course of one week starting from January 1, 2020. The data show clear daily cycles with temperature fluctuations, highlighting typical diurnal patterns where temperatures decrease during the night and increase during the daytime.

3.2 Simulating Maximum Vapor Pressure

The maximum vapor pressure was simulated to resemble the characteristics observed in the real weather dataset. Like air temperature, maximum vapor pressure exhibits both annual and daily periodic trends. However, the behavior of the daily trend varies based on the time of year, with notably higher daily amplitudes during the warmer months (see Figure 3). Several key differences were observed between maximum vapor pressure and air temperature. One difference is that maximum vapor pressure values are strictly positive; there are no negative values. Another difference is that the daily metrics (e.g., mean, amplitude, and variance) display clear seasonal variation when plotted throughout the year.

Figure 3: Maximum vapor pressure (in mbar) measured over a full year starting from January 1, 2020. The data show a strong seasonal pattern, with vapor pressure gradually increasing during the spring and peaking in the summer months (around day 200), followed by a decline in the fall and winter.

The mean value of maximum vapor pressure exhibits a sinusoidal pattern across the year, while both the amplitude and the variance of daily behavior show log-sinusoidal behavior (see Figure 4). Consequently, maximum vapor pressure was modeled as a series of daily sinusoids with time-varying mean, amplitude, and variance. Specifically, the daily mean was generated using a sine curve with added random noise, and the daily log-amplitude and log-variance were also generated from sinusoidal curves with additional noise. Noise terms were introduced using the R function `gen.arma.wge` in the `twsgc` package, simulating an autoregressive AR(1) process to add temporal dependence. While the simulated maximum vapor pressure values tend to appear slightly higher overall compared to the real data, the overall realizations capture the major seasonal patterns and variability well (see Figure 5).

Figure 4: Daily mean of maximum vapor pressure (in mbar) over the course of one year beginning January 1, 2020. The seasonal trend is evident, with vapor pressure increasing through the spring, peaking during the summer months, and declining into the fall and winter. The daily averaging smooths out short-term variability, highlighting the underlying annual pattern.

Figure 5: Single realization of the simulated daily mean of maximum vapor pressure (in mbar) over the course of one year starting January 1, 2020. The real data (blue) are compared against the simulated daily mean without noise (red) and with added noise (green). The simulation captures the underlying seasonal trend with a sinusoidal structure, while the added noise introduces realistic variability consistent with observed data.

A comparison between the real and simulated maximum vapor pressure values over the course of a full year shows that the simulation captures the overall seasonal pattern observed in the real data (see Figure 6). Both datasets exhibit an increase in vapor pressure during the spring, a peak during the summer months around day 200, and a gradual decline into the fall and winter. The simulated data, however, tend to show slightly higher variability and occasional extreme values compared to the real observations. Despite this, the simulations replicate key structural features such as the timing of the seasonal peak and the daily fluctuations. The added variability in the simulations is a result of the noise terms introduced to mimic natural atmospheric randomness. Overall, while minor differences exist, the simulated maximum vapor pressure values closely resemble the behavior of the real data.

Figure 6: Real and simulated maximum vapor pressure (in mbar) over a full year starting January 1, 2020. Real data (blue) and simulated data (red) both exhibit the expected seasonal trend, with increasing vapor pressure through the spring, a peak during summer months, and a decline in the fall. The simulated values capture the general seasonal shape and variability.

3.3 Simulating Dew Temperature

Dew point temperature was simulated similarly to air temperature and maximum vapor pressure, exhibiting both daily and annual periodic trends. However, unlike maximum vapor pressure, the amplitude of the dew point temperature's daily variation did not show as much seasonal fluctuation. Specifically, the amplitudes during the summer months were comparable to those during the winter months, indicating a more stable daily behavior year-round. The simulation of dew point temperature was therefore designed to mimic this observed stability, while still preserving the daily and seasonal cycles inherent to the real-world data.

Figure 7: Dew point temperature (°C) recorded over the full year beginning January 1, 2020. The data show a clear seasonal trend, with dew temperatures increasing through the spring, peaking in the summer months, and declining during the fall and winter. Daily fluctuations are present throughout the year.

The process of modeling dew point temperature was similar to that of maximum vapor pressure; it was modeled as a series of daily sinusoids with a time-varying mean, amplitude, and variance. The daily mean of dew point temperature was generated using a sine curve with added random noise, and the daily amplitude and log-variance were also generated from sinusoidal curves with additional noise. Noise terms were introduced using the R function `gen.arma.wge` in the `twsge` package.

To evaluate the quality of the simulated dew point temperature data, the simulated values were compared to real-world observations at two different scales: a single week (Figure 8) and the full year (Figure 9). Figure 8 shows the real and simulated dew point temperature values over the first week. Both series exhibit a clear daily cycle with alternating peaks and troughs, consistent with the known daily pattern of dew point temperature. The simulated data captures the overall structure of the daily variation, although it tends to underestimate the amplitude compared to the real data, resulting in a slightly dampened pattern.

Figure 8: Real and simulated dew point temperature values over the first week. The real data (blue) shows slightly higher variability and peak values compared to the simulated data (red), which captures the overall daily cyclical behavior but with a lower amplitude.

Figure 9 extends the comparison of the simulated data and the real data to a full-year time scale. The simulated dew temperature data accurately reflects the major seasonal trend, including the gradual increase in temperatures during the warmer months and subsequent decrease during the colder months. The overall sinusoidal shape of the annual cycle is preserved in the simulation. However, compared to the real data, the simulated series demonstrates slightly higher variability on a day-to-day basis, with more extreme fluctuations appearing throughout the year.

Figure 9: Real and simulated dew point temperature values over a full year. The simulated data (red) captures the general seasonal cycle observed in the real data (blue), including the rise and fall in mean dew point. The simulated data show similar daily variability compared to the real observations.

Overall, the simulated dew point temperature closely mirrors key real-world patterns in both short- and long-term behaviors. Small discrepancies, such as the underestimation of daily amplitudes in the first week and the overestimation of daily variability across the year, point to areas for potential refinement in future iterations. Nonetheless, the simulation provides a realistic foundation for generating synthetic datasets suitable for controlled model evaluation. Given the close alignment between the simulated and real-world dew point temperature patterns, air temperature can then be generated using the simulated dew point temperature and maximum vapor maximum data.

3.4 Air Temperature as a Combination of Exogenous Variables

Air temperature was simulated as a function of two exogenous variables: maximum vapor pressure (“VPMax”) and dew point temperature (“TDew”). To investigate how to best model the relationship between these variables and air temperature, both linear and nonlinear combinations were explored.

Figure 10: Air temperature simulations compared to real data over the full year. The real data (blue) are plotted alongside simulated temperatures generated using a linear model (red) and a nonlinear model (green).

For the linear model, air temperature was estimated using the following equation:

$$Air\ Temp_{Linear} = -2.274 + (0.815 \times VPMax) + (0.236 \times TDew) \quad (5)$$

The linear combination of air temperature in equation (5) produced a root mean squared error (RMSE) of approximately 1.595, indicating reasonable alignment with the observed air temperature values².

² See Appendix A for the autocorrelation function (ACF), spectral density, and cross correlation function (CCF) plots of the simulated air temperature data using equation (5).

Recognizing potential nonlinearities in the relationship between maximum vapor pressure, dew point temperature, and air temperature, a nonlinear transformation of maximum vapor pressure was introduced. Specifically, maximum vapor pressure was transformed according to:

$$VPMax Transform = \frac{17.62 - \left[\log\left(\frac{VPMax}{100}\right) \right]}{243.5 \times \left[\log\left(\frac{VPMax}{100}\right) \right]} \quad (6)$$

The log transformation in equation (6) effectively relates vapor pressure to temperature³. With the transformed maximum vapor pressure variable, the nonlinear model for air temperature could then be specified as:

$$AirTemp_{Nonlinear} = 45.386(VPMaxTransform) + 0.0210(VPMax) - 0.001(TDew) + 57.5(VPMax \times TDew) \quad (7)$$

As a result of the nonlinear approach in equation (7), the RMSE was dramatically lowered to approximately 0.016, indicating a very close fit to the observed air temperatures.

3.5 Model Selection

Model development was conducted using the real dataset. Since the simulations were determined to be adequately similar to the real dataset, any model created based on the real dataset should be appropriate for the simulated datasets.

ARIMA. Several ARIMA models were considered before deciding on a final model, including Vector Autoregressive Moving Average (VARIMA) model from the Darts Python package, the Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average with exogenous regressors (SARIMAX) model in Python, and the Vector Autoregression (VAR) model in R. Although these models able the underlying sinusoidal structure of the time series, they produced higher error metrics compared to simpler alternatives. For example, as shown in Figure 11, the VAR model reproduced the cyclical pattern of the air temperature data but consistently overestimated its magnitude relative to observed values.

³ Although the formula performed well empirically, it would be ideal to trace this transformation back to a more formal or peer-reviewed source.

Figure 11: VAR model forecast of air temperature, showing predicted values (red) compared with real observed data (blue) over the final five days (horizon = 720) in the dataset.

The lowest forecast errors were obtained using a sequential modeling strategy in R, in which maximum vapor pressure and dew point temperature were each forecasted independently using univariate ARIMA models. The two forecast series were then combined linearly, and the residual noise from this combination was modeled using a third univariate ARIMA. For all three ARIMA models, the differencing parameter was fixed at $d = 0$, and the seasonal period was specified as $s = 144$ to reflect the length of the observed seasonal cycle. The autoregressive (p) and moving average (q) parameters were selected by minimizing the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The resulting specifications were as follows:

- Maximum vapor pressure: ARIMA(9,0,5)
- Dew point temperature: ARIMA(7,0,5)
- Residual noise after linear combination: ARIMA(4,0,1)

Figures 12-13 present the forecasts for maximum vapor pressure and dew point temperature produced by the final model specifications; Figure 14 shows the resulting forecast of air temperature using a linear combination of the two exogenous variables.

ARIMA(9,5 with s = 144): Last 720 Observed + Forecasted - VPMax

Figure 12: ARIMA(9,0,5) maximum vapor pressure forecasts with seasonality = 144. The plot compares the last 720-time steps (5 days) of the observed values (black) and the corresponding model forecasts (blue).

ARIMA(7,5 with s = 144): Last 720 Observed + Forecasted - TDew

Figure 13: ARIMA(7,0,5) dew point temperature with seasonality = 144. The plot compares the forecasted values (blue) to the actual observed values (black) for the last 720-time steps (5 days).

Figure 14: ARIMA(4,0,1) air temperature forecasts. The plot shows the forecasted values of air temperature (blue) in degrees Celsius and the actual observed values (black) for the last 720 -time steps (5 days).

TFT. Model selection as it relates to the TFT primarily involves optimizing hyperparameters. The TFT model was implemented in the Darts package in Python. It utilized an input length of 1,440-time steps (10 days) and an output length of 720-time steps (5 days), reflecting the target forecast horizon. The model used a hidden size of 32, three (3) long short-term memory (LSTM) layers, and eight attention heads, with a dropout rate of 0.2 to reduce overfitting. After testing on 20, 30, and 40 epochs, training was ultimately conducted with a batch size of 128 over 30 epochs. This number of epochs achieved the lowest MSE for the 720-step horizon while requiring less time than 40 epochs.

Optimization employed the Adam optimizer (learning rate = 0.001) with mean squared error as the loss function. Cyclical time features (e.g., day of the year) were encoded using sinusoidal transformations and categorical datetime attributes for both historical and future windows. A fixed random seed ensured reproducibility, and `force_reset` was enabled to initialize the model from scratch at training start.

4. Results

To compare forecasting accuracy between ARIMA and TFT models, 50 simulation runs were conducted for each four different forecast horizons: 96, 192, 336, and 720⁴. Five comparisons of the ARIMA and TFT were conducted: 1) on the linearly combined simulated data (baseline comparison), 2) on the linearly combined data with 50% less variance, 3) on the linearly combined data with doubled variance, 4) on the linearly combined data with a 50% reduction in training data, and 5) on a nonlinear combination of the exogenous variables. The mean squared error (MSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) were calculated for each of the 50 runs and then averaged across all runs.

Baseline Comparison. Results presented in Table 1 show that ARIMA consistently outperforms TFT across all horizons on the baseline comparison. Each metric in Table 1 is averaged over 50 MSEs from each of the 50 simulations. Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of the 50 MSEs for both models on a horizon of 720. A Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was also used to determine the statistical

⁴ Horizon lengths were selected to replicate the results reporting structure of Zeng et. al (2023). The selected horizon lengths also ensure the models were evaluated on both shorter- and longer-term horizons. Note: data are in 10-minute intervals so a horizon of 720 is equal to a horizon of 5 days.

significance of the differences between the baseline error metrics between the two models. This non-parametric test was used due to the right-skewed (i.e., non-normal) distribution of the error metrics as seen in Figure 15.

Table 1: Baseline error metrics. Mean squared error (MSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) for the ARIMA and TFT are calculated as the mean of 50 runs on the baseline comparison on the data. The results show that ARIMA achieves consistently lower error values, with the performance gap widening at longer forecast horizons. Wilcoxon Signed Rank test p-values indicate that ARIMA significantly outperforms TFT across all horizons (***) $p < 0.01$.

<i>Horizon</i>	<i>MSE</i>			<i>MAE</i>		
	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Wilcoxon Signed Rank P-value</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Wilcoxon Signed Rank P-value</i>
96	3.566	15.957	5.21 e-6***	1.497	3.138	7.50 e-6***
192	4.279	17.612	1.53 e-6***	1.620	3.293	2.84 e-6***
336	5.573	19.813	2.47 e-6***	1.842	3.460	3.43 e-6***
720	8.879	22.941	1.28 e-6***	2.351	3.728	1.34 e-6***

Figure 15: Distribution of MSE of the TFT and ARIMA on the baseline comparison with a horizon of 720. The ARIMA model exhibits a tighter concentration of MSE values near zero, whereas the TFT shows a wider spread with more high-error instances.

Reduced Variance by 50%. There were several points of noise sources that were reduced by 50% for this comparison, including the variance parameters for both maximum vapor pressure and dew point temperature⁵, and the residual noise after the linear combination of the two exogenous variables. By reducing the variance in the simulated datasets, both models produced notably lower error metrics than the baseline comparison (see Table 2). Specifically, the MSE values decreased by approximately 50% for ARIMA and by roughly the same proportion for TFT, while MAE values decreased by about 30% for both models. These results suggest that both ARIMA and TFT are sensitive to noise levels in the data, but the performance gap between them remained consistent, with ARIMA continuing to outperform TFT across all forecast horizons.

⁵ Variance parameters include the variance of the mean, amplitude, and the variance itself (i.e., the variance of the variance).

Table 2: Reduced variance error metrics. Mean squared error (MSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) are reported for each forecast horizon, along with the multiplicative factor relative to the baseline dataset. Both models show substantial reductions in error, with MSE decreasing by roughly half and MAE by approximately one-third, and TFT exhibiting a slightly larger proportional decrease in MAE compared to ARIMA.

<i>Horizon</i>	<i>MSE</i>			<i>MAE</i>		
	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>
96	1.855	0.520	8.700	0.545	1.855	0.734
192	2.238	0.523	8.823	0.501	2.238	0.726
336	2.920	0.524	9.186	0.464	2.920	0.723
720	4.720	0.527	11.013	0.480	4.729	0.726

Increased Variance (Double). In increasing the variance of the simulated data, the same sources of noise reduced in the variance reduction test were instead doubled for this test. As shown in Table 3, both ARIMA and TFT experienced notable increases in error relative to the baseline. For both models, the MSE increased by approximately 1.8-1.9 times and the MAE increased by about 1.3-1.4 times across all horizons. Despite the performance degradation, ARIMA continued to outperform TFT at all horizons. These results suggest that while higher variance adversely affects both models, the relative ranking of performance between ARIMA and TFT remains unchanged.

Table 3: Increased variance error metrics. Mean squared error (MSE) and MAE are reported for each forecast horizon, along with the multiplicative factor relative to the baseline dataset. Variance parameters for maximum vapor pressure, dew point temperature, and residual noise were doubled relative to the baseline. Results show higher error values for both models under increased variance, with ARIMA consistently outperforming TFT across all horizons.

<i>Horizon</i>	<i>MSE</i>			<i>MAE</i>		
	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>
96	6.615	1.855	30.225	1.894	1.988	1.328
192	7.814	1.826	31.076	1.764	2.168	1.339
336	10.294	1.847	34.314	1.732	2.485	1.349
720	16.301	1.836	40.832	1.780	3.134	1.333

Reduced Training Set. When the size of the training set was reduced by 50%, factor values for both ARIMA and TFT remained close to 1.0 across all forecast horizons (see Table 4). This indicates that forecasting performance was minimally affected by the reduction in training data. For the simulated data used in this study, both models were relatively robust to reductions in training data size, with ARIMA exhibiting marginally greater stability.

Table 4: Reduced training set error metrics. Mean squared error (MSE) and MAE are reported for each forecast horizon, along with the multiplicative factor relative to the baseline dataset. Both models showed slight increases in error compared to baseline when trained on 50% less data, with ARIMA maintaining consistently lower error metrics across all horizons. Multiplicative factors indicate that ARIMA was less sensitive to reductions in training data volume compared to TFT.

<i>Horizon</i>	<i>MSE</i>			<i>MAE</i>		
	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>
96	3.351	0.940	16.352	1.025	1.468	0.981
192	4.117	0.962	17.306	0.983	1.604	0.990
336	5.473	0.982	19.293	0.974	1.837	0.997
720	8.945	1.007	21.753	0.948	2.334	0.993

Nonlinear Data. Introducing a nonlinear relationship between maximum vapor pressure and dew point temperature substantially increased the error metrics for both models, with a notably greater impact on the ARIMA (Table 5). Across all forecast horizons, the ARIMA MSE increased by over double the baseline (2.1-2.9 times), while the TFT’s MSE increased by slightly less than double (1.8-1.9 times). The mean absolute error followed a similar trend, in that the ARIMA had a greater error increase than the TFT compared to the baseline comparisons. Though the TFT was less affected than the ARIMA by the nonlinear data when compared to the baseline linear data, the ARIMA still outperformed the TFT in the error metrics across all horizons.

Table 5: Nonlinear data error metrics. Mean squared error (MSE) and MAE are reported for each forecast horizon, along with the multiplicative factor relative to the baseline dataset. Both models produced increased error metrics with nonlinear data compared to the baseline data, with ARIMA showing larger proportional increases across all horizons.

<i>Horizon</i>	<i>MSE</i>			<i>MAE</i>		
	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>Factor</i>
96	7.464	2.093	29.403	1.843	2.185	1.460
192	10.165	2.376	31.748	1.803	2.469	1.525
336	14.079	2.527	36.265	1.830	2.929	1.590
720	21.828	2.431	43.946	1.916	3.697	1.573

5. Discussion

5.1 Interpretations

Across all five comparisons and forecast horizons, ARIMA consistently outperformed the TFT (see Table 6). Given the simulated data and parameter settings used in this study, the results suggest that ARIMA was generally more effective for the forecasting task under the tested conditions. The higher error metrics observed for TFT should not be interpreted as evidence that it is unsuitable for time series forecasting in general. Instead, these findings indicate that ARIMA was better suited to the specific data characteristics, experimental conditions, and parameter configurations used in this study.

The variance reduction test provided additional insight into the models’ sensitivity to noise. When variance was reduced by 50%, both models showed substantial decreases in MSE and MAE, but the proportional improvement was generally greater for TFT than for ARIMA. This result suggests that TFT’s performance is more negatively impacted by and more sensitive to higher noise levels compared to the ARIMA. This finding is further supported by the TFT’s performance when the variance was doubled. While both models experienced notable increases in the error metrics when the variance was doubled, the proportional increase was generally larger for the TFT.

Table 6: Summary of average mean squared error (MSE) values for ARIMA and TFT models across all experimental conditions and forecast horizons. Results show ARIMA’s consistently lower MSE compared to TFT across all scenarios, with both models showing sensitivity to changes in variance, training data size, and data nonlinearity.

<i>Horizon</i>	<i>Baseline</i>		<i>Variance Decreased (50%)</i>		<i>Variance Increased (2x)</i>		<i>Nonlinear Combination</i>	
	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>	<i>ARIMA</i>	<i>TFT</i>
96	3.56	15.95	1.85	8.70	6.61	30.22	3.35	16.35
192	4.27	17.61	2.23	8.82	7.81	31.07	4.11	17.30
336	5.57	19.81	2.92	9.18	10.29	34.31	5.47	19.29
720	8.87	22.94	4.72	11.01	16.30	40.93	8.94	21.75

When the target variable was generated from a nonlinear combination of exogenous variables, both models’ performance degraded. However, the proportional increase in error was greater for ARIMA. This finding is consistent with the theoretical strengths of transformer-based architectures, which are better equipped to capture nonlinear relationships and complex dependencies in data. While ARIMA still maintained lower error metrics in this test, TFT’s relative improvement in handling nonlinear patterns suggests that it may be a more suitable choice in conditions where strong nonlinear interactions are expected.

5.2 Implications

The results of this study offer practical guidance for selecting between ARIMA and the TFT in applied forecasting contexts. ARIMA consistently outperformed TFT across all experimental conditions and forecast horizons, indicating that it is generally more reliable when working with relatively smaller datasets or noisier time series. The reduced and increased variance tests support this conclusion. While both models produced substantially higher error metrics under higher noise conditions, the proportional increase was greater for TFT. This suggests that ARIMA maintains more stable performance when data variability is high.

Conversely, the nonlinear combination tests suggest conditions in which TFT may offer an advantage. Although ARIMA still achieved lower absolute error values in these tests, TFT’s performance degraded less when the target variable exhibited nonlinear interactions with its predictors. This suggests that TFT may be better suited for applications where complex, nonlinear relationships are expected.

Taken together, these findings suggest a general decision rule: ARIMA is preferable in scenarios characterized by limited or noisy datasets, while TFT may be the preferable choice in nonlinear settings with sufficient training data. However, as with any modeling approach, the most appropriate choice ultimately depends on the specific characteristics of the data and the forecasting task at hand.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research

While the simulation framework allowed for multiple realizations (50 runs per model per forecast horizon), all simulated datasets in this study followed the same generation process: base patterns were created using a series of sine curves, noise was introduced using an ARIMA process, and the target variable was defined as a linear combination of the exogenous variables (with the exception of the nonlinear data comparison). Due to the use of ARIMA-based noise generation, it could be possible that the simulated data favored the ARIMA model. Future research may explore different data simulation methods and see how that affects each model’s performance.

Additionally, while the models were evaluated on a nonlinear combination of the data in one test, it is important to note that even the nonlinear data were still relatively simple. The TFT is especially known to do well with high-dimensional data that has complex behavior (Lim et al., 2021). The

simulated data in this study only contained 2 exogenous variables (i.e. the data is low-dimensional). Further, while 52,704 observations may be more than sufficient for the ARIMA, this data size is relatively small for the TFT. More data could possibly benefit the TFT model as transformer-based models generally perform better with more training data. Both the low-dimensional data and relatively small dataset could have been a limiting factor in the TFT's performance.

Another notable limitation of this study was the substantial computational demand required to train the TFT. Each training run of the TFT model took approximately nine hours, even when utilizing supercomputer GPUs. These high resource requirements restricted the ability to scale up the number of simulations and explore more optimal hyperparameters. Future researchers who may have access to more computational resources may consider replicating this study with thousands more realizations and further fine-tuning of the TFT hyperparameters.

Other suggestions for future research on this topic include: generating simulated data guided by other real-world datasets that exhibit different behaviors (e.g., differences in seasonality, periodic behaviors, changing amplitudes over time), and comparing performance of additional models, possibly other transformer-based models. Lastly, since this research is a methodological comparison of two different models with simulated data, there are no immediate ethical concerns.

6. Conclusion

This study compared the classical statistical ARIMA to the deep learning TFT architecture using simulated data. Fifty realizations, each containing 52,704 observations, were generated and evaluated across four forecast horizons (96, 192, 336, and 720) under five experimental test conditions: 1) baseline comparison, 2) reduced variance (50%), 3) increased variance (doubled), 4) reduced training data (50%), and 5) nonlinear combination of the target variable. Across all horizons and test conditions, ARIMA consistently achieved lower average error metrics than TFT. This outperformance by the ARIMA persisted when variance was reduced, variance was doubled, and training data were reduced by 50%. With the nonlinear combination of the target variable, both models experienced performance degradation and though the ARIMA was proportionately affected more, it still maintained lower error metrics than the TFT.

Overall, the findings support a general decision rule in model selection for time series forecasting: ARIMA is likely to be the more effective choice in scenarios characterized by limited, noisy, or low-dimensional datasets, particularly when computational efficiency is a priority. The TFT, on the other hand, may be more suitable in high-dimensional, nonlinear contexts when ample training data and computational resources are available. As with any modeling decision, the most useful model ultimately depends on the specific characteristics of the data and the specific forecasting task at hand. Future research should expand the range of simulated conditions, incorporate real-world datasets, and explore other transformer-based architectures to further evaluate the comparative strengths of ARIMA and TFT.

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Appendix

Figure 16: ACF of air temperature in the real dataset compared to ACFs from the first 20 simulated datasets. Autocorrelation functions (ACFs) were calculated for the air temperature variable to assess similarity in temporal correlation structure. The comparable decay patterns between real and simulated datasets indicate that the simulations preserve a reasonable level of autocorrelation.

Figure 17: Spectral density function of air temperature in the real dataset compared to the first 20 simulated datasets. Calculated for the first 20 days of each dataset to compare dominant frequencies. The overall shape and peak structure of the simulated spectral densities closely match those of the real dataset, suggesting alignment in periodic behavior.

Figure 18: Spectral density function centered at frequency $1/144$ (0.007). This zoomed view highlights the expected daily periodicity. Both real and simulated datasets display a clear peak at this frequency, confirming preservation of the daily cycle.

Figure 19: Spectral density function for summer months. Computed for the middle 20 days of the dataset to contrast seasonal patterns with winter months. The simulated datasets reproduce the general frequency structure of the real data, with only minor deviations near higher frequencies (~ 0.5).

Figure 20: CCF of maximum vapor pressure and dew point temperature in the real dataset compared to simulated datasets. Cross-correlation functions (CCFs) were calculated to assess temporal relationships between maximum vapor pressure and dew point temperature. While the correlation at lag=0 is well preserved, discrepancies emerge at lags greater than ± 30 -time steps, suggesting potential refinements for future simulation.